

The Case Method for Teaching Philosophy

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Abstract:

Based on an examination of specific limits in philosophy education when professors employ presentation and question-and-answer methods, the article emphasizes the necessity to reinvent philosophy teaching methods in order to promote active and creative pupils. Among active teaching approaches, the article chose the case method to supplement the traditional teaching method, which has frequently occupied a unique position in teaching philosophy up to now.

Keywords: *active teaching methods, innovate philosophy teaching methods, teaching philosophy.*

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Introduction

Following the Ministry of Education and Training's strategy of innovating the teaching of Marxist-Leninist science disciplines in colleges and universities, the teaching and learning of philosophy has achieved certain results over time. Students are more active and proactive through discussion and group work because lecturers use modern teaching aids and know how to construct student-centered classes. However, the philosophy section, often known as Basic Principles of Marxism-Leninism 1, is not particularly popular among students. This fact is caused by a variety of circumstances. The popular teaching style for lecturers is still "teacher reads, student copies," with little practical expertise, making class hours demanding and tedious. Because the school frequently believes that this is a common subject, many classes are combined, resulting in high class sizes and disorderly class periods because it is difficult for teachers to supervise. Students, on the other hand, have not really focused on listening to lectures, have not turned the learning process into a self-study process, and have relied

heavily on rote learning and coping learning. This condition necessitates greater innovation in teaching, learning, and evaluation methods, with teaching method innovation having a direct and decisive impact on the quality of philosophy teaching.

Current Philosophy Teaching Methods

In Vietnam, colleges and universities have used innovative philosophy teaching methods to promote students' positivism and creativity. The traditional teaching style, in which the lecturer teaches and the pupils listen and take notes, remains the most popular. Teaching philosophy today mostly use presentation and question-and-answer approaches. The effectiveness of these two strategies cannot be questioned, but if abused or misused, they will result in poor teaching quality and effectiveness. Because they are ideal for big classrooms, these two methods are frequently utilized by lecturers teaching Marxist-Leninist science subjects; yet, due to the nature and peculiarities of philosophy as a

theoretical discipline. In comparison to the cognitive level of first-year students, it is abstract and complex.

Philosophy professors quickly discover that speaking for an extended period of time exhausts students because they must sit and listen without actively engaging in the class. Lecturers are also anxious and exhausted due to time constraints and content to impart. Most students are apprehensive and have little interest in learning this subject, especially when the lecturer lacks the capacity to talk and instead relies solely on a presentation style. Because students are unable to participate, collaborate, or offer their thoughts, instructors are unaware of what subject students have grasped and what content has to be revised. In fact, when adopting one-way communication, pupils cannot retain all of the philosophical content offered by the lecturer, and may remember only a portion of it. Because there is only one-way presentation without feedback, students' and lecturers' ability to remember-understand-apply has not been fully utilized.

In addition to the presenting approach, one of the most often utilized methods in teaching philosophy nowadays is question and answer. The question and answer technique is essentially a sort of class discussion in which the lecturer asks questions, students respond, and the lecturer comments and responds. Using this strategy causes students to actively listen and pay attention to the lesson; lecturers are relieved of the responsibility of delivering. But how can you use questions to complement the lesson's topic and objectives? It is worth examining how to ask questions at the correct time and in the right location while adhering to the principles of moderation and augmentation in teaching. In truth, many lecturers today have not engaged in developing a question system while creating courses, resulting in arbitrary questioning in class that is inappropriate for the target audience, such as questions that are too simple or too complex. The questions are overly long, and they are elevated in every subject, resulting in boredom and difficult classes. If the lecturer asks and answers too many questions during a teaching session, it will result in "burning the lecture"

owing to wasting a lot of time, especially with difficult topics. When students answer questions, however, lecturers do not have the practice of responding, analyzing, praising, and inspiring them, so they cannot increase instructional effectiveness.

Using erroneous traditional methods, the lecturer is at the center and appears to be primarily responsible for the success and quality of philosophical lectures. As a result, kids' self-discipline, positivism, initiative, and originality in learning are lost. Students are unable to exercise the habit of self-study and self-research, lack philosophical critical thinking, and are unable to communicate nonverbally. Students, in particular, lack the ability to apply and answer philosophical challenges encountered in everyday life. Some philosophical principles and categories, such as cause and effect; nature, phenomena; the connection is frequent and develops...but lecturers do not capitalize on students' comprehension and application. Students always have the mindset of "the teacher does it for the students," sit and wait, rely on each other, and have the habit of listening without offering comments, thus discussion hours are merely a formality. For example, following the presentation of the group leader, most students agreed and did not have the practice of asking questions to clarify philosophical concerns. As a result, remembered knowledge is unsustainable. Thus, if only traditional methods are used to teach philosophy, the effectiveness will be low, and training costs will be ineffective at the macro level.

The problem is that traditional ways of teaching philosophy are less successful, generating weariness in both lecturers and students, and the quality of training is low, so should we use this method? Presentation and question and answer are, in our opinion, fundamental methods appropriate to the nature and peculiarities of this subject. However, this should not be considered the only technique, and additional active teaching methods such as game methods, discussion and group work methods, situational methods, and breakout methods should be used flexibly. tape... Only then will students' acquired

knowledge be more sustainable, and it is critical to know how to apply and articulate their opinions on a philosophical topic posed in life.

Applying the Case Method to Teaching Philosophy

To improve the quality and efficacy of teaching, it is vital to use teaching approaches that foster students' initiative, positivism, and creativity in learning, in addition to standard teaching methods. The case method of teaching is one of the ways that can eliminate passive learning and textbooks while also training students' problem-solving and critical thinking skills.

"A situation is a whole set of events that happen in a place, at a time, or at a time," according to the Vietnamese Dictionary. From the preceding premise, it is clear that problems emerge in everyday life that demand people to think, deal, or solve in order to be productive at work and in life.

A teaching situation is a tale that portrays a real or imaginary incident or setting in order to accomplish the lesson objectives. Situations are constantly dramatic, and disputes present several opportunities for association and resolution. As a result, instructional situations are frequently incomplete stories. The essence of the case teaching method at the university level is that by addressing scenarios, students learn coping abilities, confidence, and the flexibility to deal with real-life challenges.

Philosophy is a science that studies the most general rules of nature, society, and thought, yet those basic laws must be represented in specific ways. As a result, teaching philosophy must be linked to actual life, with theory illuminating practice and practice verifying the scientific nature of theory. The case method of teaching philosophy overcomes the theoretical and abstract nature of the subject; students do not have to learn general philosophical principles and rules but can instead solve real issues. As a result, it improves comprehension and the ability to apply philosophical ideas, laws, and categories in everyday life. Simultaneously, adopting the case method makes class more interesting,

stimulates student interest and attention, and increases students' passion for this subject.

For instructors, the most critical stage in successfully implementing the case method is preparation. During the preparation phase, lecturers must select existing scenarios that they have gathered or created themselves. Choose the right circumstance based on the instructional goals. The scenario must be current and realistic; students must be able to come up with different answers; and the situation's material must be correct and appropriate to the student's level, compatible with the subject's goals and criteria. For example, in philosophy, there are situations and concerns linked to how to consider the genesis of the universe according to two materialist trends (the material world is what precedes birth and determines the beginning of the world). consciousness) and idealism (consciousness, the spirit of "god, god" is the origin of the material universe, it precedes and influences the material world). When considering the universe, people, and life, the situation's content is a discussion or portrayal of two viewpoints: materialism and idealism. To create a tense atmosphere, the final paragraph of the issue does not remark, does not provide solutions, or raises questions; students must think about the solution. For example:

Dialectical materialism is the first chapter.

1. The conflict between materialism and idealism in resolving fundamental philosophical difficulties

Instructors can assign students to answer the following problems:

Student Minh and student Trang had the following debate about the genesis of all species:

"There are countless different species of animals and plants in the world today." It is so wealthy because God created it first; even humans were created by God." Trang pondered and responded, "I believe your concept is incorrect." There are no gods in this earth. Things differ because they exist and adapt to their surroundings.

Whose point of view do you agree with?

Mention the perspectives of two pupils, Minh and Trang.

The goal of the preceding scenario is to assist students understand that in order to have a correct worldview and view of life, human life requires a dialectical materialist perspective when considering phenomena.

The lecturer intends to divide the group, give tasks, establish the time, and orient how to manage the scenario after preparing the specific circumstance and questions connected to the problem. The following phase is to plan for implementation. In order to successfully utilize the case method, lecturers must have group teaching skills as well as classroom organization skills in addition to a strong awareness of teaching scenarios.

The lecturer introduces the scenario and delivers information to each student or group of pupils. There are numerous methods for disseminating knowledge about the scenario (distributing documents, using videotapes, speaking in class, and encouraging students to role-play). The lecturer gives each student time to read and learn about the situation. The time will be determined based on the duration, content of the lecture, complexity of the situation, and class size. The instructor must guarantee that all of the students in the class understand the scenario. To debate the situation, the professor splits the students into groups. Clearly define the tasks that the group must do, the time frame, and the manner in which the group will work. When groups talk, trade, and discuss, does the lecturer need to visit each group to ensure that they are on the right track? Do you need assistance? Following the conclusion of the conversation, the groups present the outcomes of their group's management of the scenario in the form of a role play, with the entire class expressing their thoughts. The success of the case approach will be determined by the success of this open discussion (in which the entire class exchanges and debates together). When students discuss a problem, the lecturer can take notes, summarize what has been accomplished, provide comments, evaluate, and finally resolve the issue.

Case Example: How to Consider Phenomena

How to proceed is as follows:

First, build situational goals.

By resolving the issue "How to Consider Phenomena," students will get knowledge and understanding of dialectical and metaphysical procedures. Students understand how to apply the substance of dialectical methods and metaphysical ways to explain and evaluate practical difficulties encountered in everyday life, as well as how to consider phenomena from a dialectical perspective.

Second, provide details regarding the situation's content.

Mr. Hoa took advantage of the opportunity to get a haircut after finishing his farm job. He asked the barber after the haircut, "How much money will it take for you to pay?"

While cleaning, the barber respectfully replied, "Yes, thirty thousand dong, sir." Mr. Hoa was perplexed: "Why is it so expensive?" I only took 20,000 dong a few months ago." The barber went on to say, "Sir, lately all expenses have doubled, from food, gasoline, electricity, water, and the rent for this shop has also increased." His expression was irritated: "The prices of food, electricity, water, gasoline, and restaurant rentals have indeed increased, but what does that have to do with haircuts?" "You "slash" way too much!" Despite this, Mr. Hoa took out his money to pay. His heart was still full with bitterness when he left. Student A stated that the barber's reasoning was highly dialectical after hearing Mr. Hoa's story from beginning to end. and Mr. Hoa's argument was metaphysical. Do you agree with student A's opinion? Why?

Third, state the student's tasks.

Students must use their philosophical knowledge of dialectical and metaphysical approaches to assess whether the barber's and Mr. Hoa's points of view are dialectical or metaphysical. What are the legitimate points of view to explore, and what conclusions should be reached regarding how to interpret things and phenomena?

Fourth, there are directions for implementation.

The scenario described above can be used to teach Chapter 2: Materialist Dialectics. Students majoring in Economics and Business Administration are subjects. The barber, Mr. Hoa, and student A are chosen by the lecturer to play the roles. The class size is between 30 and 40 people. Writing board and large paper are examples of educational media. The classroom is big enough for groups to work together.

Instructors organize themselves in the following steps:

- Step 1: Students learn about the circumstance and select three students to perform different roles.
- Step 2: Form groups to discuss: Depending on the number of students and the time available, divide them into groups.
- Step 3: Students meet in groups to discuss.
- Step 4: Each group elects a person to speak.
- Step 5: Hold a class discussion regarding the issues provided.
- Step 6: The instructor concludes the discussion and the subject.

Following the debate, the lecturer must assist students in realizing:

- Student A is correct in his assessment that Mr. Hoa's argument is metaphysical, but the barber's argument is dialectical. I agree with student A's point of view. Specifically:
 - According to the barber, the increase in haircut pricing is due to the effect and impact of costs such as higher food, gasoline, electricity, and water prices, as well as shop rent. The barber in this case analyzed things and phenomena in terms of their interrelation, influence, binding, and mutual regulation. As a result, the barber's point of view expresses a dialectical point of view. Mr. Hoa, on the other hand, believes that the rise in food prices, energy, water, gasoline, and shop rent is unconnected to the price of haircuts. In this case, Mr. Hoa considered the

incident in isolation, so Mr. Hoa's argument expressed a metaphysical viewpoint.

- When studying and evaluating occurrences in life, we must adopt a dialectical approach. Nothing in the objective universe sits stationary because all things and occurrences are linked and interact with one another. As a result, when studying and assessing items or phenomena, it is required to consider and evaluate them in connection to other things. As a result, it is appropriate for the barber to raise the price of haircuts, but it is not appropriate for him to take advantage of the increase in gasoline costs to make illicit profits by raising the price of haircuts too high.

Teaching philosophy through scenarios has several advantages, including increasing the practicality of philosophy by applying philosophical concepts, rules, and categories to concrete problems and phenomena in life. Aids in the clarification of philosophical ideas, rules, and categories. Philosophical information is reinforced and developed by specific scenarios, pupils remember more steadfastly, and they are able to adjust to changing actual world. However, the way students present and handle issues will provide teachers with many interesting ideas to expand their lectures and earn a lot of experience when using the case method. Furthermore, teaching philosophy through scenarios has various problems and difficulties, such as expanding the lecturer's expertise and time. Because philosophical situations are not readily available, instructors must devote time and effort to writing, collecting, and researching. The case approach necessitates more complicated abilities than the (conventional) presentation style, such as how to organize the class, schedule time, ask questions, and lead the class in discussion, criticism, and feedback. review. Furthermore, in order to effectively handle situations, lecturers must master professional knowledge, have a comprehensive understanding, constantly update fresh information, and master pedagogical abilities. When using this strategy, lecturers have a significant hurdle. Furthermore, the attitude of "teachers do things for students," sitting and waiting, laziness, and less cooperation

are still prevalent in students' learning habits. The ability of first-year students to reason and answer philosophical problems is limited. Most students are afraid and think that this is a difficult subject, so they lose confidence when solving situations.

According to the above analysis, lecturers must perform the following activities in order to have rich, fascinating, and current situations:

For starters, lecturers develop the habit of collecting, studying, and publishing cases. The content of philosophical circumstances must be realistic and contemporary, expressing people's life concepts and daily lives in society... In order to meet the instructional objectives, situations must closely match the learning object. Use hilarious and clever remarks to make the scenario more vibrant and appealing.

Second, when the groups have presented, the lecturer comments and rates them to encourage students to participate more actively. Lecturers should not be impatient or dwell on the mistakes and limitations of the groups in order for students to be more confident in the subsequent discussion hours.

Third, create a bank of philosophical scenarios. Currently, collecting and writing philosophical teaching circumstances is not only limited from a personal standpoint, but it is also extremely constrained. The quality and efficiency of philosophy departments will improve greatly if they establish proactive banks of philosophical circumstances. Professional interaction and connection between schools are required at the macro level. This is a necessary requirement for improving professional qualifications as well as the existing level of human resource training.

Conclusion

Improving the quality of philosophy instruction necessitates a number of elements, one of which is the development of novel teaching methods, which will contribute to long-term improvements in training quality. The case method of teaching philosophy aids in the training and development of vital abilities for

students such as analytical skills, problem solving, presenting skills, expressive skills through role-playing... As a result, students have a better knowledge of the lesson's content and objectives, avoiding rote learning, inactivity, waiting, and procrastination when studying and investigating philosophy. To get good results, lecturers must actively engage in self-study and research, acquire pedagogical skills, and be adaptable in their teaching techniques. The case method is just one of the teaching methods, so philosophy lecturers need to combine it with other pedagogical methods to improve the effectiveness of their lectures.

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